

Collective Velocity and Entropy in Classical Statistical Mechanics

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The spatial density in classical statistical mechanics for a system with a temperature T and potential $V(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. This factor is sometimes obtained using the ideal gas law Pressure = density $R T$ and enforcing that pressure at two close points balance the mass times the force $(-d/dx V(x))$ of the region in between. In other cases, it is obtained from considerations of the Boltzmann transport equation. In other cases still, it can be obtained by maximizing entropy subject to constraints. These various pictures do not seem to bring in the idea of collective velocity which should be present. Instead, they are somewhat static. In this note, we wish to attempt to describe the origins of the factor $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ in terms of collective velocity. We wish to then link it to entropy and finally consider the idea of flux.

Traditional Ways of Obtaining $\exp(-V(x)/T)$

The spatial density in a classical statistical mechanical system with $V(x)$ can be obtained in a number of ways. In (1), the ideal gas law is used to obtain the pressure at two very close points using $P = \text{density } R T$. This pressure difference is then said to balance the density * volume * $-dV(x)/dx$ of the tiny region in between the two points. This approach bypasses any consideration, at least explicitly, of collective kinetic energy. It is a static picture.

In (2), it is assumed that $f(x,p) = f(p) \exp(-V(x)/T)$ and then it is verified that this solution satisfies the time dependent Boltzmann transport equation.

Finally, we consider obtaining $\exp(-V(x)/T)$, at least formally, by maximizing Shannon's entropy:

$-k d(x) \ln[d(x)] + b d(x)V(x)$ where b is a Lagrange multiplier and $d(x)$ the density. In other words, one is considering different density arrangements which would give the same overall potential energy, but would maximize entropy. Again, there do not seem to be explicit references to collective velocity produced by $V(x)$.

Effects of Collective Velocity

In order to view the effects of collective velocity, let us examine a system with $V(x)$ and with two walls at temperature T . At each wall, we assume no collective kinetic energy, so the potential energy for each particle there is $V(\text{wall})$. Given that the wall is at a temperature T , the particles near each should have a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution proportional to $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$.

One can always add a normalization constant. This distribution can be thought of as maximizing entropy subject to a constraint on energy, or it can be arrived at from Boltzmann's transport equation:

$$f(p_1)f(p_2) = f(p_3)f(p_4) \quad ((1))$$

Here p_1, p_2, p_3 and p_4 are momentum vectors, conservation of momentum and kinetic energy apply and $f(p)$ is the probability density for momentum p . This equation can be solved, yielding

$$\text{number}^{(\text{conserved quantity}(p))}$$

This can be rewritten as $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$ where kinetic energy is the conserved quantity used. Statement ((1)) comes from the Boltzmann equation, but seems to be a direct statement of independent probability. One considers time reversal and argues that the probability to create p_3 and p_4 from p_1 and p_2 is also the probability to create p_1 and p_2 from p_3 and p_4 , so $f(p)$ densities do not change. ((1)) seems to be a fundamental result.

Let us now consider a system with a potential $V(x)$ which is sparse so that particles only scatter against the walls where one has a potential of $V(\text{wall})$. At any point in the system, one can consider the reaction $p_1, p_2 \rightarrow p_3, p_4$. It seems, however, that one does not know how p_1 and p_2 are obtained. For example, $f(p_1)$ may represent the distribution of p_1 at a point x . Particles in this distribution, however, came from the wall and were accelerated by the potential. Thus, by ((1)), relative probabilities at x suggest that $f(p)$ is proportional to $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$. On the other hand, we have the distribution of the velocity at the wall which will become v at x . In other words, at the wall we need a particle with a velocity v_{wall} such that:

$$.5mv_{\text{wall}}^2 + V(\text{wall}) = .5mv^2 + V(x) \quad ((2))$$

We know that distribution at the wall so $f(v_{\text{wall}}) = \exp(-.5mv_{\text{wall}}^2/T)$. Given that the potential will accelerate v_{wall} , $v_{\text{wall}} < v$. Thus $\exp(-.5mv_{\text{wall}}^2/T) > \exp(-.5mv^2/T)$. This seems to explain why the density for v is higher at x than it is at the wall where $f(v \text{ at the wall}) = \exp(-.5mv^2/T)$. Thus, the particles at the wall have a certain distribution with weights. The weights stay the same as one moves along the potential, but the kinetic energy (velocities) change. Thus, different velocities become associated with the original weights. This leads to a shift in density. Originally one had $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$ at the wall, but a more prevalent (higher probability), but lower velocity at the wall moves along and becomes v at x . Thus, it looks like the density of v at x has somehow increased. This argument shows explicitly the importance of collective velocity. It should also yield explicitly the form of $d(x)$ (density of x).

At x , we want two particles with velocity v_1 and v_2 for ((1)) (even though no actual collision is going to occur). The relative probabilities should be $\exp(-.5mv_1^2/T)/\exp(-.5mv_2^2/T)$. At the wall, the particles which will lead to v_1 and v_2 have a relative probabilities of:

$$\begin{aligned} f(v_1) &\text{ proportional to } \exp(-1/T (V(\text{wall}) - V(x) - .5mv_1^2)) \text{ and} \quad ((3)) \\ f(v_2) &\text{ proportional to } \exp(-1/T (V(\text{wall}) - V(x) - .5mv_2^2)) \end{aligned}$$

The relative $f(v_1)/f(v_2)$ is the same, but ((3)) contains explicit space dependent information. This, it seems, leads to $d(x)$ proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. One can think of the density at the wall as being proportional to $\exp(-(.5mv^2 + V(\text{wall}))/T)$. Here $V(\text{wall})$ is a constant so it does not cause problems.

Entropy Considerations

It is argued that ((1)) can be used to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann velocity distribution, but it can also be obtained from maximizing entropy, as is done in many books. This applies to the velocity distribution, but what about the spatial result $d(x)$ proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$? It was argued in the previous section that $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ arises simply by different weights from the maximization of entropy at the wall being reassigned to different velocities due to the extra collective velocity added by the potential as the particles move along x . Thus, there does not need to be a major rearrangement of particles in space, it happens naturally under the effects of the potential $V(x)$. In other words, $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ is a consequence of the maximization of entropy for the velocity only case. A different $d(x)$ would disrupt this maximum entropy. Thus, $d(x)$ of the form $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ is the solution which allows for maximum velocity entropy. In principle, it does not need to be calculated from the extremization of entropy, it follows directly from it. Nevertheless, given that one writes $f(v)$ proportional to $\exp(-(.5mv^2 + V(\text{wall}))/T)$ as maximizing entropy, then $\exp(-(.5mv^2 + V(x))/T)$ should also maximize entropy. In addition, at x the velocity pieces are supposed to maximize velocity entropy, so:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{density} &= f(v)g(x) \text{ then Entropy} = \int dv dx f(v)g(x) \ln[f(v)g(x)] \\ &= \int dv dx f(v)g(x) [\ln(f(v)) + \ln(g(x))] = \int dv f(v) \ln(f(v)) + \int dx g(x) \ln(g(x)). \end{aligned}$$

Maximizing overall entropy seems to be equivalent to maximizing spatial and velocity entropy at point x . Thus, each can be maximized separately, subject to appropriate constraints. Thus, this may justify the approach of maximizing: $-d(x) \ln(d(x)) + b V(x) d(x)$.

Flux

The approach used in this note, argues that Maxwell-Boltzmann probability distribution at the wall keeps its same form, but that the potential converts one velocity into another, giving the appearance of a density change. This argument does not use flux, yet given that there is collective motion, it might be good to consider some issues related to flux. In particular, we note that in classical mechanics (3), $1/v(x)$ is used to describe the density of a single particle (with no temperature) moving along x which has a potential $V(x)$. This result is equivalent to $d(x_1) v(x_1) = d(x_2) v(x_2)$. At first, it might seem that there is no density in the case of a single particle, but one can picture cutting space and time into equal $\Delta x \Delta t$ units and noting that in regions where the particle moves quickly, it spends less time, i.e. a smaller fraction of Δx . Thus, its density goes down as it passes with weight 1 for $dt/\Delta t$ and with weight 0 for the rest of the

$\delta(t)$ interval. This density is then linked to quantum mechanics for high energy eigenfunctions.

A question arises as to what link exists between the classical mechanical $1/v(x)$ and classical statistical mechanics? The statistical mechanical density seems to be based on relative weights. For example, one asks: If the probability of v_1 at the wall is P_1 what is the probability of v_1 at x ? It is higher, because a lower energy, higher probability particle at the wall will ultimately become v_1 at x . This it seems explains the density increase at x . It appears one is dealing with conditional probabilities $P(p/x)$. The particles in the sparse gas may not arrive at x at the same time, so one can even consider a long time average to determine the spatial density. For example, if one follows a single particle in a sparse gas and notes its velocity every time it collides with a wall, it will take some time to establish that the distribution is a Maxwell-Boltzmann one.

$1/v(x)$ is of a different nature. It describes the time spent by a particle as it moves through dx . It predicts high densities for low velocities, the opposite result of $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. In (4), we attempted to reconcile the two by considering fluxes, namely:

At x , the particle has a density of $1/v(x)$, but the flux velocity is taken at $x-dx$, namely $v(x-dx)$. The flux = $v(x-dx)/v(x) = 1 - dx dv(x)/dx = 1 + dV(x)/dx (1/v(x)*v(x))$. This is somewhat similar in appearance to the statistical mechanical result:

$$d(x)/d(x+dx) = 1 + dx d/dxV(x) (1/T)$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that the spatial density factor $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ in classical statistical mechanics can be understood from the collective motion shifting velocities of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, so that high weight low velocity situations retain their high probability weight, but increase their velocity due to the potential (extra collective velocity). This makes it look like there is an increase in density. The weights which can be obtained by maximizing entropy, do not change, so the resulting spatial distribution, proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$, is also directly related to maximum entropy and can be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to appropriate constraints.

Reference

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